

TRICHILIA.

- spondioides.* 1-2. T. foliis impari-pinnatis subhirsutis, pinnis sub-10-jugis, inferioribus majoribus, racemis axillaribus. T. *spondioides.* Jacq. am. 128. Sloan h. 2. 103. t. 210. 2. 3. *Jamaica, Hispaniola.* ♀.
- pallida.* 2-3. T. foliis impari pinnatis membranaceis, racemis axillaribus terminalibusque, floribus octandris, filamentis villosis, capsulis 2-valvibus. *Hispaniola.* ♀.
- moschata.* 2-3. T. foliis pinnatis, pinnis alternis, racemis compositis, floribus sub 10-drus 1-petalis, fructibus 1-spermis. Laurus folio brevior, flore racemoso minore — Sloan, h. 2. p. 21. t. 166. f. 2. *Jamaica,* ♀.

MELIA.

- sempervirens.* 1-2. M. foliis bipinnatis, foliolis rugosiusculis subseptenis. M. *Azedarach.* b. Linn.

OCHNA. LINN. (LII.)

Cal. 5-phyllus. *Cor.* 5-petala.

Antheræ subsessiles.

Drupæ receptaculo incrassato subrotundo carnososo insertæ.

(inter *Quassiam* & *Fagoniam.*)

- nitida.* 2. O. calycibus corollæ æqualibus, drupis receptaculo superimpositis, foliis ellipticis serratis. *India occidentalis.* ♀.
- Iabotapita.* 1. O. petalis calyce 3-plo majoribus, drupis receptaculo immersis. O. *Iabotapita.* Linn.

QUASSIA.

- excelsa.* 2-3. Q. floribus hermaphroditis 5-drus paniculatis; foliis impari-pinnatis, foliolis oppositis, petiolatis, petiolo nudo. *Jamaica.* ♀.

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descriptionum vegetabilium, maximam partem
incognitorum quae sub itinere in Indiam Occidentalem
annis 1783-87 digessit Olof Swartz, M.D.**

Holmiae [etc.]In Bibliopoliis Acad. M. Swederi,1788.
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MAXIMAM PARTEM INCOGNITORUM

QUÆ

SUB ITINERE IN INDIAM OCCIDENTALEM

ANNIS 1783—87

DIGESSIT

OLOF SWARTZ. M. D.

HOLMIÆ, UPSALIÆ, & ABOÆ,

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MDCCLXXXVIII.

1788